

This paper has been published as: Labie, M., Méon, P-G., Mersland, R. & Szafarz, A., (2015), “Discrimination by microcredit officers: Theory and evidence of disability in Uganda”. The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance. Vol. 58(4), 44-55.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2015.05.002>

ORCID (Roy Mersland): 0000-0002-6683-2737

Discrimination by Microcredit Officers: Theory and Evidence on Disability in Uganda[⊗]

Marc Labie

Université de Mons (UMONS), Warocqué School of Business and Economics, humanOrg &
CERMi, Email: Marc.Labie@umons.ac.be

Pierre-Guillaume Méon[•]

Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Solvay Brussels School of Economics and Management,
Centre Emile Bernheim, Email: pgmeon@ulb.ac.be

Roy Mersland

University of Agder, Norway, & CERMi, Email: roy.mersland@uia.no

Ariane Szafarz

Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Solvay Brussels School of Economics and Management,
Centre Emile Bernheim, & CERMi, Email: aszafarz@ulb.ac.be

[⊗] The authors wish to thank the editor and an anonymous referee for useful comments. They also acknowledge comments by Cécile Abramowicz, James Copestake, Simon Cornée, Bina Fernandez, Rients Galema, Andre Guettler, Niels Hermes, Bruce Wydick, and participants to the Annual Meeting of the American Economic Association, Denver (January 2011), to the CERMi/Oxford Workshop “Microfinance’s Contribution to Development Studies. What Interdisciplinary Approaches Add to Microfinance Understanding?”, Brussels (January 2010), and to the Second International Research Workshop on Microfinance Management and Governance, Kristiansand (September 2009). All remaining errors and approximations must be blamed on one of the authors, on whose identity they will not agree.

[•] Corresponding author.

Discrimination in Microfinance: Theory and Evidence on Disability in Uganda

Abstract:

This paper studies the relationship between a microfinance institution (MFI) and its loan officers when officers discriminate against a particular group of micro-entrepreneurs. Using survey data from Uganda, we provide evidence that loan officers are more biased than other employees against disabled micro-entrepreneurs. In line with the evidence, we build an agency model of a non-profit MFI and a biased loan officer in charge of granting loans. Since incentive schemes are costly and the MFI's budget is limited, the MFI faces a trade-off between combating discrimination and granting loans. We show that the optimal incentive premium is a non-decreasing function of the MFI's budget. Moreover, even a non-discriminatory welfare-maximizing MFI may let its loan officer discriminate, because eradicating discrimination would come at the cost of too many loans. Observing an MFI's loan allocation biased against a minority group therefore does not imply that the institution is biased against this group.

Keywords: Microcredit; micro-entrepreneurs; discrimination; loan officers; incentives; disability.

JEL codes: G21, O16, J33, L3.

1. Introduction

Claiming that pro-poor microfinance institutions (MFIs) might discriminate against some micro-entrepreneurs may understandably sound like an oxymoron. Indeed, pro-poor MFIs consider providing financial services to the poor and the unbanked as a top priority (Hudon, 2009). Moreover, they are often sponsored by charitable foundations that take pride in their own good reputation. Those foundations would be put at risk if the institutions they support were suspected of discriminating against customers based on race, gender, or other characteristics. For these reasons, pro-poor MFIs are unlikely at first glance to purposely discriminate against sub-groups of their potential clientele.

However, evidence of discrimination in the credit market abounds. In an influential paper, Black *et al.* (1978) showed that race matters in mortgage loan allocation. Using information collected by the Federal Reserve Bank of Boston, Munnell *et al.* (1991, 1996) spurred a large literature by finding that non-white applicants were significantly more likely to be denied a mortgage loan than white applicants with similar profiles. Discrimination is also detected in small-business lending. Cavalluzzo and Cavalluzzo (1998) find that businesses owned by Hispanics and blacks face higher loan denial rates than those owned by whites. Blanchflower *et al.* (2003) report that black-owned small businesses are about twice as likely to be denied as white-owned ones, holding all other factors constant. Cavalluzzo and Wolken (2005) and Blanchard *et al.* (2008) confirm those results.

Admittedly, this evidence originates in the U.S. There is, however, ground to believe that discrimination in credit allocation is also present in developing countries, where populations are often ethnically mixed and few legal barriers to discrimination exist.¹ Storey (2004) shows that in Trinidad and Tobago, loan applications from African-descendant small-business owners are more likely to be denied than others. Buvinic and Berger (1990),

¹ Discriminatory practices have been exhibited in developing countries, notably India and in Latin America. In some cases, discrimination is direct: belonging to a given community generates social obligations and economic deprivation, as shown by Thorat (2002) with caste discrimination. In other cases, discrimination is indirect: lower human capital endowment is associated with lower access to education, causing a part of the population to be pushed into poorly-paid “dead-end jobs” (Knight, 1985). As stated by Patrinos (2000), indigenous, ethnic, racial, and linguistic minorities tend to be in an inferior economic and social position in comparison with the rest of the population.

Fletschner (2009), Agier and Szafarz (2012a, 2012b), and Brana (2012) provide evidence that women are more credit-rationed than men by MFIs.

Several authors report that MFIs discriminate against disabled micro-entrepreneurs. Lewis (2004) stresses that businesswomen with disabilities in Zambia and Zimbabwe do not get access to microfinance services. Cramm and Finkenflügel (2008) and Bwire *et al.* (2009) point out that discrimination by MFI staff is a major reason why disabled people find it hard to access microfinance. This is confirmed by a recent study by Beisland and Mersland (2012a) showing that 22% of economically active disabled persons do not approach MFIs for fear that the staff will reject them because of their disabilities.

Discrimination is a disappointing but acknowledged reality worldwide. Questioning its existence in microfinance not only makes sense; it is particularly relevant as poverty and discrimination often overlap (Patrinos, 2000), and access to credit has proved crucial to the poor. In addition, microfinance portfolios are known to exhibit biases in favor of some customers, such as traders and urban dwellers. Whether those biases originate from efficiency motivation or from bigotry among MFI staff is still mostly unexplored. As far as poverty alleviation is concerned, detecting discriminatory practices in microfinance is a major task, not only for researchers, but also for practitioners.

Addressing discrimination in micro-lending requires a precise definition to start from. The definition proposed by Schreiner *et al.* (1996, p.849) states that: “*Discrimination* is defined as providing smaller loans and/or providing loans with more stringent terms to borrowers who are identical with respect to creditworthiness but who differ with respect to characteristics unrelated to creditworthiness, such as race.” This definition is somewhat restrictive, because creditworthiness is not the sole criterion used in micro-loan granting. Welfare-maximizing institutions such as MFIs have a double-bottom line (Tulchin, 2003), namely financial and social. Therefore, we have used a more general definition compatible both with mission statements and with financial constraints. In line with Dymiski (2006), we define discriminatory micro-lending as denying loans more frequently and/or granting loans with more stringent terms on the basis of observable characteristics unrelated to both creditworthiness and the MFI’s mission. For instance, if the MFI’s mission is serving poor entrepreneurs, then the institution is said to discriminate against a specific group of borrowers

if loans are granted to members of this group less easily and/or with harsher conditions than to other borrowers with similar levels of both poverty and creditworthiness.

Our definition has two dimensions. Given the possible interplay between both bottom lines, discrimination is trickier to detect in socially-oriented MFIs than in standard for-profit institutions. Consider, for instance, the case of discrimination against the disabled. First, within a pool of equally-poor micro-entrepreneurs, discrimination may lead to denying loans to some disabled applicants even though they are more creditworthy than non-disabled applicants who receive a loan. Second, within a pool of same-creditworthiness micro-entrepreneurs, discrimination may lead to favoring less poor applicants from the non-disabled group. In addition, discrimination may also arise from the combination of both these mechanisms (Agier and Szafarz, 2011). However, in such a case, at least one criterion must be strictly fulfilled since the trade-off between poverty and creditworthiness is MFI-specific, and cannot be attributed to discrimination.

Surprisingly, little academic research in microfinance takes discrimination as a main focus. This paper aims at filling this gap. We argue that discrimination in microfinance finds its origin in the decentralized governance of MFIs. MFIs are indeed highly decentralized. Typically, clientele selection is delegated to loan officers, who are poorly monitored, at least as far as their day-to-day work goes. Decentralization gives considerable leeway to loan officers, who spend up to 75% of their working time outside of the office (McKim and Hughart, 2005), and are difficult to monitor. This situation is reinforced by the wide demand-supply gap still existing in microfinance (Cull et al., 2009). If it exists, discrimination in microfinance could result from the behavior of loan officers. Since the managers of MFIs do not look at the personal characteristics of borrowers, discrimination by loan officers would remain undetected.

In this paper, we set up a formal model to investigate how a welfare-maximizing MFI may use incentive wage contracts to deter its loan officers from discriminating. Over the last decade, incentive pay has become increasingly common in MFIs (*Développement International Desjardins*, 2003, Holtmann and Grammling, 2005). The share of MFIs that resort to staff incentive schemes grew from 6% in 1990 to 63% in 2003 (McKim and Hughart, 2005). Nevertheless, existing incentive schemes are associated with financial output rather

than with social mission, which makes them mostly inefficient against discriminatory practices.

To our knowledge, this paper is the first to draw the theoretical consequences of taste discrimination in a welfare-maximizing (as opposed to profit-maximizing) lending institution that does not have to cope with competition as a disciplining device. In particular, our model emphasizes that the MFI faces a trade-off between fighting discrimination and extending outreach, because incentive contracts are costly and the budget is limited. Welfare maximization may thus not imply complete eradication of discriminatory practices. In equilibrium the MFI may be better-off paying a smaller incentive premium, and letting its loan officers discriminate to some extent.

The paper is organized as follows. In the next section, we use data from Uganda, and report evidence that loan officers tend to discriminate more than other staff. Our results moreover suggest that discrimination is due to distaste rather than biased beliefs. In line with the evidence, we set up the model and draw its key implications in Section 3. Section 4 concludes.

2. Discrimination by Loan Officers: Evidence

In microfinance, loan officers play a key role in screening loan applicants.² They meet applicants face to face, and might therefore be inclined to discriminate against some of them. Although screening criteria are fairly standardized, loan officers are difficult to monitor. Owing to decentralization and poor supervision, they can discretionarily grant loans to their preferred micro-entrepreneurs rather than serve the whole target population of the MFI. Privileged borrowers could, for instance, belong to the officers' social network.³ Additionally, loan officers may be reluctant to interact with some minority groups, such as the disabled. In this section, we present evidence that the disabled are subject to discrimination, based on a survey conducted in Uganda.

² On the role of loan officers, see Fuentes (1996), Warning and Sadoulet (1998), Schreiner (2000), and Tchakoute-Tchuigoua (2012).

³ Evidence of cultural affinity in lending is provided by Bostic (2003). Ferguson and Peters (1997) discuss the implications of cultural affinity.

According to the United Nations (2008), approximately 10% of the global population has disabilities, and 80% of the disabled live in developing countries. Among those who live on less than one dollar a day, one in five is disabled. Although the vast majority of disabled persons are able to work, 80 to 90% have no formal job. As a consequence, they turn to self-employment (UN, 2008). Few have access to microfinance provided by banks and MFIs.

In Uganda, the incidence of disability ranges from 3.5% (Population and Housing Census, 2002) to 20% (Uganda Demographic and Health Survey, 2006), depending on the statistical method. However, only 0.5% of MFIs' customers are disabled (Bwirre *et al.*, 2009). Beisland and Mersland (2012b) find that economically active disabled persons often turn to informal financial sources. While 66% belong to member-based savings and credit clubs, only 15% service a loan. On average, the disabled are poorer than the rest of the population (UN, 2008). According to our definition, this should make non-discriminatory pro-poor MFIs serve them more swiftly than other applicants with the same creditworthiness. But do disabled entrepreneurs exhibit the same creditworthiness as non-disabled ones? Even though disabled entrepreneurs are poor, they are largely involved in diversified economic activities. The adult disabled populations of developing countries are often affected by relatively mild sight, hearing, or other impairments that could have been treated in more developed countries. It is also a sad fact that Ugandan children with severe disabilities often do not reach adult age. In addition, Martinelli and Mersland (2010) report that disabled entrepreneurs receive operational support from relatives and friends. Although MFIs market fair lending policies, few disabled people can access their services. Remarkably, this does not prevent most of them from running viable businesses.

As Neufeldt (1995) points out, disability is essentially a social construct with roots in societal attitudes. Accordingly, Johnson and Lambrino (1985) attribute more than one third of wage differences between the disabled and the non-disabled to taste discrimination. Peck and Kirkbride (2001) exhibit the unspoken fears related to the hiring of people with disabilities. Employers are often reluctant to hire disabled people, particularly if they have not done so previously. They perceive the disabled as less productive *per se* even when they are not so (Blanc, 2010). Evidence suggests that even anti-discrimination legislation does not eradicate discrimination against the disabled (see Barnes and Oliver, 1995, for the U.K., and Beegle and Stock, 2003, for the U.S.). Overall, researchers have repeatedly demonstrated that being disabled is associated with exclusion, similarly to discrimination on the grounds of race, sex,

or tribe. While direct evidence on the creditworthiness of disabled borrowers is still lacking, there is ground to believe that their access to credit is limited by discrimination rather than by objective credit assessment.

Our survey data was collected in Uganda in 2008-2009 by the Association of Microfinance Institutions of Uganda (AMFIU) in a joint initiative with the National Union of Disabled Persons of Uganda (NUDIPU). The Norwegian Association of the Disabled (NAD) supports AMFIU and NUDIPU in their efforts.⁴ The project includes field training for 750 staff members from 75 MFI branches in issues related to microfinance and disability. In 24 branches, training started by filling out the questionnaire of this survey. In addition to reporting personal data and their position in the branch, the respondents were asked to rate their attitudes and beliefs about microfinance and disability on a one-to-five scale. Eight MFIs are represented in the database, ranging from two small Savings and Credit Cooperatives (SACCOs) to the largest MFIs in Uganda. All MFIs represented in the dataset pursue outreach to economically poor customers while at the same time being financially sustainable, the so-called ‘promise’ of microfinance (Morduch, 1999). They also claim a non-discriminatory practice when it comes to gender, religion, disability, etc. The 24 branches are located across the country in eight out of Uganda’s 80 districts. The dataset consisting of 231 respondents is representative for staff working in Ugandan MFIs. Among them, 66% are loan officers. Table A2 in the Appendix provides descriptive statistics on the respondents.

Credit officers are responsible for mobilizing, screening and monitoring the micro-entrepreneurs. Their recommendation are key in deciding whether an applicant receives a loan or not (Agier and Szafarz, 2013a). The other employees are branch managers, deputy managers, cashiers, or sit on what is often called the “information desk”. Cashiers and information clerks have little influence on decisions, and their contact with customers is limited to receiving payments and handing out applications and brochures. Their job is not to assess customers, but to carry out predefined “secretarial” duties. Last, Branch managers are squeezed between main office's directions and credit officers’ demands.

Among the 231 respondents in our survey, 133 are credit officers, 68 are not credit officers and 30 give no information. Interestingly, 54 respondents report having a leadership

⁴ One of the authors has participated as a consultant for NAD in its efforts to extend outreach of microfinance to disabled people in Uganda.

position, among whom 24 also report being credit officers. This means that either the MFI is small enough for the branch manager to also be in charge of a credit portfolio, or the branch is bigger and a senior credit officer is supervising the junior credit officers. In sum, out of the 68 non-credit officers 30 are managers and 38 are cashiers or information clerks.

The study focuses on the reactions to statements addressing discrimination. To make our analysis robust, we use two statements: one phrased as “we discriminate” and the other as “we never discriminate.” A respondent who may be reluctant to agree with the statement “we discriminate” may find it easier to disagree with the statement “we never discriminate,” and vice versa.

The respondents were asked to rate on a one-to-five scale their agreement with the two following statements:⁵

1. *“I believe that one of the reasons why we have few disabled customers is because we often unconsciously marginalize or discriminate them”.*
2. *“I believe that in this branch we never discriminate against people because of their disability”.*

Given that discrimination is a highly sensitive topic that can drive a so-called “social desirability bias” (Nederhoff, 1985), the statements are formulated in the plural (“we”), not in the singular (“I”) in order to be less offensive to the respondents. Nevertheless, we interpret the reactions to these statements as directly related to the respondent’s own behavior.

Figure 1 displays the rating distributions for both statements, splitting the sample across loan officers and other employees (secretaries, office clerks, and branch managers). In both instances, ratings span the whole scale, and differences appear between loan officers and other employees. In Figure 1a, the mode of statistical distribution concerning statement 1 (“we often discriminate”) is 4 (“partly agree”) for loan officers, and 1 (“fully disagree”) for other employees. While 56% of the loan officers partly or fully agree with statement 1, only

⁵ Table A1 in the Appendix gives the full set of ratings. Although not perfect, the correlation between the reactions to the two statements is significantly negative. The Spearman rank coefficient is equal to -0.268 and statistically significant well beyond the 1% level. Moreover, most individuals are consistent. For instance, 78% of the respondents who fully disagree with the statement “we often discriminate” either agree or fully agree with the statement “we never discriminate.”

30% of the other employees do. A similar picture emerges from Figure 1b regarding statement 2 (“we never discriminate”). More precisely, 63% of the loan officers fully disagree with statement 2 against 49% of other employees.

*** Insert Figure 1 here ***

Overall, the raw figures suggest that discrimination is more prevalent among loan officers than among other MFI employees. Loan officers probably discriminate more than other employees because they are in a position to do so. To check whether these numbers are statistically significant and to determine from what kind of behavior they originate, we turn to econometric analysis.

We regress the reactions to statements 1 and 2 on the respondent’s characteristics. Since the explained variables are discrete and ordered, we resort to ordered logit models.⁶ A dummy explanatory variable captures whether the respondent is a loan officer or another MFI staff member. The sign of the coefficient associated with this variable signals whether loan officers tend to discriminate against the disabled more or less than their co-workers do. The dataset allows us to control for other characteristics. We include explanatory dummies for having a disabled relative,⁷ being female, and having at least three years’ work experience.

Admittedly, differences in attitudes towards disabled borrowers could be attributable to differences in information about their creditworthiness. According to the economic theory of discrimination initially applied to the job market, discrimination may result from two mechanisms. First, the statistical discrimination theory builds on the possibility that employers who doubt that workers from a given group have the required skill will discriminate against this group. This theory, based on asymmetric information, was initiated by Phelps (1972) and Arrow (1973), and later formalized by Coate and Loury (1993). Second,

⁶ Using ordered probit models does not change the results significantly.

⁷ We checked the difference in the beliefs of respondents between those who have a disabled relative and those who do not. A t-test fails to reject the null hypothesis that the difference between the mean answers of the two groups is zero at standard levels of significance. An ordered logit regression of the answer to the question about beliefs on the disabled relative dummy led to the same conclusion.

the theory of taste-based discrimination, originated by Becker (1957), rests on the assumption that employers simply lose utility when they hire a worker from an identified group. In a nutshell, the statistical theory blames discrimination on beliefs, while the taste-based theory blames it on preferences.

The distinction between statistical and taste-based discrimination also applies to the loan market. In particular, discrimination against the disabled on the microfinance market may be due to the belief that the disabled are riskier customers or to a genuine distaste for the disabled. These two types of discrimination may even coexist.

In the present case, discrimination of the disabled on the microfinance market may be due to the belief that the disabled are riskier customers or to a genuine distaste for the disabled. Both types of discrimination may coexist. Disentangling beliefs from preferences is particularly important in our study, because loan officers' beliefs might result from their field experience. Loan officers are likely better informed than other employees on their clients' creditworthiness. If the disabled were really subject to higher default risk, it could be economically justified to grant them loans less easily. In other words, if we detect that the differences in reactions to statements 1 and 2 are fully attributable to beliefs, we would need extra information on repayment conduct to check whether we are facing statistical discrimination or a profit-based attitude. To disentangle the two mechanisms, we need to control for the beliefs of MFI employees about the riskiness of the disabled. Fortunately, we are able to control for the respondent's beliefs on disabled borrowers' creditworthiness thanks to the reactions to a third statement:

3. *"I believe that being disabled is associated with higher risk of loan default".*

The respondents rate statement 3 on a one-to-five scale. If an employee believes that the disabled are riskier borrowers, then he/she might treat them differently than other borrowers whom they do not hold in distaste. Controlling for the rating of statement 3 neutralizes the impact of beliefs. The remaining effect must therefore come from taste-based discrimination.⁸ The framing of the question allows us to control for the perceived credit risk

⁸ Given the nature of our data, this argument needs to be understood in a relative way (loan officers versus other employees). The framing of the question also allows us to control for the perceived creditworthiness of the disabled.

of the disabled, which may be overestimated by non-disabled loan officers and affect their decision to grant a loan, as Johansson-Stenman (2008) argues. Moreover, the coefficient of the higher-default variable measures the importance of statistical discrimination. Namely, if that coefficient turns out large and strongly significant, then a large chunk of the observed discrimination may be attributed to statistical discrimination. Conversely, if that coefficient turns out small or insignificant, then discrimination must be related to taste.

*** Insert Table 1 around here ***

The ordered logit models are estimated with cluster-robust standard errors to control for within-branch correlations. The results are provided in Tables 1 and 2. The picture that emerges from both tables is consistent. In Table 1, the baseline regression indicates that being a loan officer yields higher discrimination. The Wald Chi-squared statistic for the likelihood ratio test confirms that adding the loan officer dummy improves the fit. Regression (1.2) captures no relationship between believing that the disabled exhibit lower creditworthiness and acknowledging discrimination. This suggests that beliefs are not a driving factor of discriminatory behavior. Hence, we exclude both statistical discrimination and profit-oriented reluctance to serve disabled borrowers. We therefore interpret our findings as evidence of taste-based discrimination.

Regression (1.3) shows that the impact of being a loan officer is robust to controlling for the respondent's belief about credit risk.⁹ In addition, this belief remains insignificant. Regressions (1.4) to (1.6) include additional controls but leave the main result unchanged. Among the controls, only the dummy for having a disabled relative passes the ten-percent significance test with a negative coefficient. This finding lends credence to interpreting the dependent variable as a valid indicator of individual discriminatory behavior. It is also reminiscent of Dymski's (2006) statement that the lack of "cultural affinity" may hurt minority loan applicants.

⁹ Moreover, a bivariate logit regression (not reported here) in which the belief is explained by the loan officer dummy reveals no link between the two variables. This means that the belief of loan officers is similar to that of other respondents.

Table 2 shows that loan officers disagree more than others with the statement “*we never discriminate*”. It also confirms that responses on discrimination against the disabled are independent of beliefs about their creditworthiness. Again, these findings are robust to the inclusion of additional controls. The only difference with Table 1 is the absence of any significant impact of having a disabled relative.

In a logit model, the coefficients cannot be directly interpreted as marginal effects, because the model is non-linear. Marginal effects can, however, be inferred from regressions for each combination of independent variables.¹⁰ Consider for instance a male employee with no disabled relative, little experience, and no clear-cut opinion on the creditworthiness of the disabled.¹¹ From Table 1 (statement: “*we discriminate*”) and specification (1.6), such an employee has a 0.39 probability of picking rating 4 (“*partly agree*”) if he is a loan officer, and 0.32 otherwise. From Table 2 (statement: “*we never discriminate*”) and specification (2.6), the same employee has a 0.25 probability of picking rating 1 (“*strongly disagree*”) if he is a loan officer, and 0.14 otherwise.

*** Insert Table 2 here ***

One may be concerned that the type of MFI affects responses to the survey. If MFIs provide relatively uniform services and operate in relatively similar markets, their legal forms and regulatory frameworks can exhibit large variations (Labie, 2001), which potentially influence their operations like for instance their lending methodology (Mersland, 2009)¹². In our sample, the four most prevalent MFI types are represented. First, traditional NGOs are

¹⁰ To do so, we use the estimated coefficients and set all control variables to their desired values. The probability of an outcome is computed as the probability of the latent variable of the model falling in the interval corresponding to that outcome. The marginal effect of being a loan officer is measured by the variation of that probability between loan officers and other employees.

¹¹ This situation is simulated by setting to zero the dummies for a woman, disabled relative, and work experience; and setting the rating of statement 3 (“higher default”) to three.

¹² Our dataset does not include information on lending methodology. We do not consider this a major problem for three reasons. First, most MFIs combine individual and group lending (Mersland and Strøm, 2012). Second, NGOs typically offer group lending more than other types of MFIs. Hence, controlling for MFI type captures reasonably well the lending methodology. Third, the group lending model practiced in Uganda typically involves individual assessment carried out by the credit officer. The group’s main function is to serve as a guarantor.

nonprofit small organizations offering only credit and operating without a license from the banking authorities. Our sample features 82 respondents working in such MFIs. Second, transformed NGOs have changed from a nonprofit status and become shareholder companies operating with a license to mobilize deposits. We have 121 respondents from such MFIs in our sample. Third, Bank MFIs are full-fledge regulated banks specializing in microfinance services. 14 respondents in our sample report working in banks. Likewise, 14 respondents work in Savings and Credit Cooperative Organizations (SACCOs) that are small member-owned organizations allowed to mobilize savings and provide loans only among members. Including type of MFI in our regressions will also control for the MFI's profit orientation which may likely influence discriminatory practice in the organization (Mersland, 2009).

Thus, to make sure that our results are not driven by MFI-type, we run new regressions and introduce MFI-type dummies among the controls, using traditional NGOs as the reference group. The results of those estimations are reported in Tables A3 and A4. Log pseudo-likelihoods show that introducing MFI-type fixed effects increases the fit of the regressions, and particularly so in Table A3, where the dependent variable is the rating of the statement “we often discriminate”. The results also reveal nuances across types of MFIs. In Table A3, the coefficients of the Bank and SACCO MFIs dummies are statistically insignificant, suggesting that discrimination in those MFIs is similar to discrimination in NGOs.¹³ In contrast, the transformed-NGO dummy exhibits a positive coefficient, suggesting that discrimination in those MFIs is stronger than in traditional NGOs. This could indicate that transformed NGOs undergo a mission drift (Armendariz and Szafarz, 2011). In Table A4, no MFI-type dummy is significant. The reactions to the “we never discriminate” statement are thus similar across MFIs. Overall, both regressions are consistent with the previous results linking the loan officer position to a higher propensity to exert discrimination against the disabled. In addition, the coefficient associated to the belief that the disabled exhibit higher credit risk is never statistically significant. Discrimination must therefore be attributed to taste.

Overall, our findings underscore a strong correlation between acknowledging discrimination and being a loan officer. They also suggest that discrimination is not

¹³ This should be interpreted with caution because of the low number of respondents in the bank and SACCO categories.

attributable to beliefs. Hence, we conclude that loan officers tend to exert taste-based discrimination. The next section investigates the consequences of such a bias for socially-oriented MFIs.

3. A Model of Discrimination by a Biased Loan Officer

The previous section made the case for the existence of taste-based discrimination by microcredit officers. Such discrimination is at odds with the poverty-alleviation mission of MFIs, not only for obvious moral reasons, but also because poverty and discrimination tend to overlap (Patrinos, 2000). In this section, we propose a model that represents discrimination as resulting from the combination of asymmetric information and the delegation of loan granting to a biased officer. In that way, taste discrimination creates a typical agency problem.¹⁴ We discuss how a socially-oriented MFI can design optimal wage incentives to combat taste discrimination by its loan officers.

3.1. The Model

In our model, three types of agents interact: the socially-oriented MFI, micro-entrepreneurs, and a biased loan officer. The MFI has a defined target population of micro-entrepreneurs. Its goal is to maximize welfare, and so to grant loans to the poorest segment of that population.¹⁵ The MFI grants individual loans and delegates clientele selection to a loan officer. The simplification of an MFI granting individual loans is in line with current changes in the industry where even pioneers like Grameen bank move away from group lending to individual lending (Dowla and Barua, 2006). This change is driven by competition (Ghatak and Guinnane, 1999), the costlier business model of following group lending (Mersland and Strøm, 2012), and the fact that most economically poor people prefer individual loans (Wydick, 2001), though maybe not the very poorest (Madajewicz, 2011). Mersland and

¹⁴ See Méon and Szafarz (2011) on discrimination as an agency problem in a set-up where shareholders maximize profit.

¹⁵ Our results therefore do not directly apply to for profit MFIs. One the difference in social performances between for profit and not for profit MFIs, one may refer to Tchakoute-Tchuigoua (2010).

Strøm (2012) report that only a fifth of MFIs offer group lending only to their clients. For a comparison of individual and group lending, see Madajewicz (2011).

The micro-entrepreneurs are split in four categories: They are either favored ($i = F$) or discriminated against ($i = D$) by the loan officer, and either poor ($\kappa = P$) or less poor ($\kappa = L$).¹⁶ Thus, any applicant has two characteristics (group membership and poverty level), of which only the first is observable to the MFI:

$$(i, \kappa), i \in \{D, F\}, \kappa \in \{P, L\} \quad (1)$$

The pool of micro-entrepreneurs features the following observable proportions of the four categories: $\gamma_{DP}, \gamma_{FP}, \gamma_{DL}, \gamma_{FL}$, with $\gamma_{ik} > 0 (i = D, F; \kappa = P, L)$ and $\sum_{i=D,F} \sum_{\kappa=P,L} \gamma_{ik} = 1$.

Assessing poverty requires detailed information, notably on income and cash flows, and only the loan officer gathers such information. Therefore, poverty levels constitute the officer's private information. The officer can thus exert discrimination in lending against members of group D by strategically hiding applicants' poverty levels to the MFI.

All loans are identical and normalized to 1. A loan allows the borrower to seize a riskless investment opportunity that yields return r (identical for all micro-entrepreneurs).

As discussed in the introduction, discrimination in pro-poor organizations can take two different – but non-mutually-exclusive – forms, namely favoring less poor F applicants and favoring less creditworthy F applicants. To keep the model simple, we assume that all loan applicants share the same probability of default. As a consequence, we abstract from the second form of discrimination.¹⁷

According to its mission statement, the MFI is benevolent and group-blind. Its objective is to maximize welfare, measured by the expected social utility of its clients:

¹⁶ In addition, we adopt several simplifications. First, in contrast to Aubert *et al.* (2009), we do not include the client's ability as a relevant characteristic, as the MFI's objective is purely social. Second, we do not discuss the MFI's inter-temporal financial sustainability.

¹⁷ Relaxing this assumption would make our model more complex, but leave its main outcomes qualitatively similar.

$$\text{Max} \sum_{j=1}^n E[U_j], \quad (2)$$

where n is the number of clients, to be determined endogenously, and $E[U_j]$ is the expected utility of client j . We assume decreasing marginal utility of income. Consequently, any given return results in a larger extra utility for a poor borrower than for one who is less poor. The extra utility brought by a loan is therefore Δu_p to a poor borrower and Δu_L to a less poor one, with $\Delta u_p > \Delta u_L$. The MFI consequently prefers granting loans to the poor than to the less poor, because loans to the poor applicants increase welfare to a larger extent.

We assume that the MFI faces a fixed budget constraint. This assumption is in line with the evidence that most socially-oriented MFIs are subsidized NGOs failing to attract profit-oriented investors (Hermes and Lensink, 2007, Cull *et al.*, 2011). The fixed budget B is to be allocated both to loans and to the loan officer's wage ω :

$$B = \omega + n.c, \quad (3)$$

where n is the number of loans to be fixed by the MFI, and c is the positive constant marginal cost associated with a loan, in addition to the loan officer's wage.¹⁸ Cost c is the sum of the operational and monitoring costs associated with a loan and the expected default loss, minus the present value of the interest differential (loan rate minus financing rate). This cost is a constant because all micro-entrepreneurs have same the creditworthiness, which implies that the expected default on a loan is identical for all borrowers.

Unlike the MFI, the loan officer is biased against the D group. This assumption is consistent both with the previous section's findings and with the evidence reported by Cavalluzzo and Cavalluzzo (1998) that minority-owned small businesses face higher denial rates attributable to taste-based discrimination. Owing to time constraints, the loan officer meets only a limited number of applicants every period, and allocates one loan in each period. For simplicity, we assume that each choice is to be made between two applicants randomly

¹⁸ Because its budget constraint is binding, the MFI makes no surplus. On the distribution of surplus among the stakeholders of MFIs, the interested reader may refer to Hudon and Périlleux (2014).

drawn from a predetermined pool.¹⁹ Due to his/her bias, the loan officer would never spontaneously grant a loan to a D applicant unless both applicants belong to that group.

The MFI is aware of the loan officer's bias, but does not observe poverty levels. As a consequence, it chooses a second-best strategy, and pays an incentive wage, which inversely relates to the loan officer's discriminatory intensity. The loan officer's reaction to that incentive is modeled in probabilistic terms. When facing two applicants with respective characteristics (D, P) and (F, L) , the officer offers the loan to the (D, P) candidate with probability $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. Variable λ measures the officer's propensity not to let prejudice interfere with loan granting.

Prejudice makes the loan officer's expected utility decrease with λ . We assume that the loan officer has the following expected utility:

$$E[V] = E[\omega] - \frac{1}{2} d \lambda^2 \quad (d \geq 0) \tag{4}$$

where ω is the loan officer's wage. Parameter d captures the intensity of the loan officer's bias against the D group. As d increases, the officer's expected disutility of choosing a poor D applicant over of a less poor F applicant increases. Parameter d therefore gauges the officer's aversion to the D group relative to his/her utility of consumption. An unbiased officer is characterized by $d = 0$, but there is no upper limit on d .

*** Insert Table 3 here ***

The outcome of the loan granting process depends on the characteristics of the micro-entrepreneurs. Table 3 summarizes the situation. The characteristics of applicants 1 and 2 are displayed in the first row and first column, respectively. The corresponding cell of Table 3 gives the loan beneficiary, and, whenever relevant, the associated probabilities. When both applicants share the same poverty level, the loan officer systematically chooses an F

¹⁹ The argument can, however, be extended to a larger number of applicants.

applicant, if any. The decision becomes trickier when the poorest applicant belongs to the D group. The officer's bias could indeed be high enough for him/her to allocate the loan to a less poor F applicant rather than to a poor D applicant.

The welfare gain associated with the characteristics of the loan beneficiary is displayed in Table 4 for each pair of micro-entrepreneurs. When the poorest applicant belongs to the D group, the loan officer's bias can be detrimental to the MFI's mission, and result in what is referred to in the microfinance literature as mission drift.²⁰ Only an incentive can make the loan officer choose applicant (D, P) over applicant (F, L) .

*** Insert Table 4 here ***

The micro-entrepreneur's poverty level is unobservable to the MFI and cannot serve as an instrument for incentivization. Instead, we assume that the incentive is inversely related to the loan officer's bias, which is assumed observable. The rationale for introducing anti-discrimination incentives is twofold. First, most socially-oriented MFIs would consider fighting discrimination as a subsidiary mission. For instance, many MFIs focus on women even in male-dominated societies (Morduch, 1999). Second, group membership is observable to the MFI, and discriminated-against groups are typically poorer than the rest of the population. Therefore, anti-discrimination incentives may be viewed as a second-best instrument.²¹ Specifically, we consider a standard linear wage contract with fixed component C and premium s :

$$\omega = C + s\lambda, \quad s \geq 0, \quad C > 0, \tag{5}$$

²⁰ The term "mission drift" usually designates the situation where the financial sustainability constraint makes the MFI move away from its poverty-alleviation mission (Armendariz and Szafarz, 2011). Allet and Hudon (2013) and Cornée and Szafarz (2014) discuss the relevance of adding environmental or ethical bottom lines to financial and social objectives.

²¹ For instance, one may argue that the MFI should prefer disabled customers to make them equal in income generating capacity.

The contract in (5) nests the standard contract in which the officer’s wage is a constant and s is set to zero. More generally, $s\lambda$ can be interpreted as the total costs of dealing with biased agents. Such costs may, for instance, include expenditures on training, monitoring, and evaluation procedures. The higher the agent’s prior taste for discrimination, λ , the higher the total cost will be. We assume a linear form for simplicity.

The interpretation of the wage contract goes beyond financial incentive. It can embed the cost of any measure the MFI is willing to implement in order to reduce the impact of its loan officer’s bias. Parameter s could for instance be a monitoring or an educational cost. In that case, ω would measure the total labor cost of credit officers. For simplicity, we however refer to s as a financial incentive.

From Eqs. (3) and (5), the MFI’s budget constraint is:

$$B = C + s\lambda + nc \tag{6}$$

Eq. (6) emphasizes that the MFI faces a trade-off. Increasing s augments the loan officer’s propensity to serve poor micro-entrepreneurs, but also raises the officer’s wage and so reduces the total number of loans to be allocated, n . The MFI has thus to trade off between serving the poor and granting more loans.

To close the model, we specify the timing of the game (see Fig. 2). The MFI first chooses n and s under the participation constraint, which states that the officer’s expected utility must exceed that provided by his/her outside option. The loan officer then determines λ , and subsequently allocates the n loans. Last, the resulting MFI’s total utility is realized.

Figure 2: Timing of the Game

3.2. Equilibrium Discrimination

The model is solved through backward induction. First, we describe the reaction function of the last player, i.e., the loan officer. Then, we derive the contract offered by the MFI, which determines the outcome of the game.

The loan officer chooses probability λ , which represents his/her propensity not to let prejudice interfere with the lending decision. Plugging the wage scheme (5) into the officer's objective function (4) yields:

$$\text{Max}_{\lambda \in [0,1]} \left\{ C + s\lambda - \frac{1}{2}d\lambda^2 \right\}. \quad (7)$$

The first-order condition is:

$$\lambda = \frac{s}{d} \quad (8)$$

Note that λ increases with the MFI's incentive instrument, s . Being a probability, λ must take values between 0 and 1.²² This restriction may in turn lead to corner solutions for some parameter configurations. Therefore, one has:

$$\lambda^* = \begin{cases} \frac{s}{d} & \text{if } s \leq d \\ 1 & \text{if } s > d \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The MFI designs the performance-based contract by anticipating its effects on the officer's behavior. From Table 4, the MFI's utility of allocating a loan to applicant j is the random variable defined by:

$$U_j = \begin{cases} \Delta u_L & \text{with probability: } \Omega(\lambda) = \gamma_{DL}^2 + \gamma_{FL}^2 + 2\gamma_{DL}\gamma_{FL} + 2(1-\lambda)\gamma_{FL}\gamma_{DP} \\ \Delta u_p & \text{with probability: } 1 - \Omega(\lambda) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

²² However, discrimination does not disappear altogether when $\lambda = 1$. Indeed, when facing two equally-poor applicants, the loan officer with $\lambda = 1$ systematically chooses the F applicant, if any. Pushing the argument to the extreme, if the pool were made up of poor applicants only, then no D applicant opposed to an F applicant would ever get a loan. The MFI has no incentive to counteract such discrimination, because it is blind to group membership.

where probability $\Omega(\lambda)$ is a linear function of λ :

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega(\lambda) &= (\gamma_{DL}^2 + \gamma_{FL}^2 + 2\gamma_{DL}\gamma_{FL} + 2\gamma_{FL}\gamma_{DP}) - 2\lambda\gamma_{FL}\gamma_{DP} \\ &= a - b\lambda\end{aligned}$$

with:

$$\begin{cases} a = \gamma_{DL}^2 + \gamma_{FL}^2 + 2\gamma_{DL}\gamma_{FL} + 2\gamma_{FL}\gamma_{DP} \\ b = 2\gamma_{FL}\gamma_{DP} \end{cases}$$

As a consequence, the MFI's problem states:

$$\text{Max}_{n,s} \sum_{j=1}^n E[U_j] = n[a\Delta u_L + (1-a)\Delta u_P - b(\Delta u_L - \Delta u_P)\lambda] \quad (11)$$

$$\text{s.t.: } B = C + s\lambda + nc$$

Let $Q = B - C$ be the MFI's net budget, $A = a\Delta u_L + (1-a)\Delta u_P$ be the part of MFI's expected utility that is independent from the officer's behavior, and $\delta = \Delta u_P - \Delta u_L$ be the extra utility of granting a loan to a poor borrower instead of a less poor one. The MFI's problem becomes:

$$\text{Max}_s E[U(s)] = \left(\frac{Q - s\lambda}{c} \right) (A + b\delta\lambda) \quad (12)$$

Given the loan officer's optimal reaction function in Eq. (9), the optimal value for s is either the interior point, \tilde{s} , or the corner value, d . To compute \tilde{s} , we rewrite the MFI's objective function for $\lambda = \frac{s}{d}$:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n E[U_j] = \frac{1}{cd^2} (-b\delta d s^3 - A s^2 + Qb\delta s + dQA), \quad (13)$$

which leads to the following first-order condition:

$$-3bd\delta s^2 - 2As + Qb\delta = 0. \quad (14)$$

Since its determinant $\Delta = A^2 + 3Qb^2 \delta^2 d$ is positive, the second-degree equation in Eq. (14) has two real roots, but only one is non-negative (because $\Delta > A^2$), and hence admissible given that s is a premium:

$$\tilde{s} = \frac{A + \sqrt{\Delta}}{3bd\delta} \quad (15)$$

The MFI's objective function reaches its global maximum for $s^* = \tilde{s}$, provided that $\tilde{s} \leq d$. Alternatively, if $\tilde{s} > d$, then (9) implies that the loan officer adopts the non-discriminatory behavior, namely $\lambda^* = 1$, so that the MFI has no incentive to offer a premium larger than d . In this case, the MFI's optimal premium is $s^* = d$. In short, we have:

$$s^* = \min\{d, \tilde{s}\} \quad (16)$$

The corresponding optimal value for λ is given by:

$$\lambda^* = \begin{cases} \frac{\tilde{s}}{d} < 1 & \text{if } s^* = \tilde{s} \\ 1 & \text{if } s^* = d \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Expression (17) displays our key result, summarized in Proposition 1.

Proposition 1:

- (i) If the MFI offers no incentive premium ($s = 0$), then in equilibrium loan officers discriminate: $\lambda^* < 1$.
- (ii) If the MFI offers the optimal incentive premium ($s = s^*$), then in equilibrium loan officers sometimes discriminate: $\lambda^* \leq 1$.

Despite being a pure welfare-maximizer and blind to group membership, the MFI may thus tolerate some discrimination in equilibrium. The rationale for this result is that fighting discrimination is costly, not only in financial terms (higher wage and training costs), but also

– and more to the point – in terms of outreach (fewer granted loans). Each extra dollar devoted to incentives reduces the number of loans. The MFI must then trade off between two evils: discrimination and poverty. If the officer’s taste for discrimination is high enough, then the social cost, in terms of foregone loans, of eradicating discriminatory behavior would be too large. In such a case, the MFI tolerates some discrimination because the marginal benefit of devoting a dollar to combating discrimination would be lower than the benefit of granting an extra loan.

Consequently, observing an MFI’s loan allocation biased against a minority group does not necessarily imply that the institution is intrinsically biased against this group. It can alternatively be the case that the MFI delegates loan allocation to biased loan officers and cannot afford to eradicate discrimination. From a managerial policy perspective, this result suggests that additional solutions must be found to combat discrimination, because wage incentives may prove insufficient. Moreover, our result is obtained on the premise that the MFI maximizes social welfare. Therefore, a benevolent social planner would adopt the exact same behavior.²³

The model has interesting additional implications. Proposition 2 describes the MFI’s optimal contract of incentive pay.

Proposition 2: The optimal incentive premium is a non-decreasing function of the MFI’s

$$\text{budget: } \frac{\partial s^*}{\partial B} \geq 0.$$

Proof: If $\tilde{s} \geq d$, the optimal premium is a constant: $s^* = d$. Alternatively, if $\tilde{s} < d$, from the

$$\text{expression of the determinant of Eq. (14), we have: } \frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial B} = 3b^2 \delta^2 d > 0. \text{ Then, Eq. (15)}$$

$$\text{implies that: } \frac{\partial s^*}{\partial B} = \frac{\partial s}{\partial \Delta} \frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial B} > 0.$$

²³ In our setting, the MFI is hurt by discrimination only insofar as this interferes negatively with its social mission. Fighting discrimination is not the MFI’s final goal. A more drastic version of our model could include fairness to the MFI’s mission statement. If this were the case, the trade-off would still not automatically disappear. However, the incentive would be higher, and the non-discriminatory equilibrium would become more likely.

The intuition behind Proposition 2 is that when the budget of the MFI, B , increases, the trade-off between allocating more loans and reducing discrimination becomes less stringent. The MFI can therefore afford to offer more powerful incentives to its loan officer. As a consequence, the impact of the MFI's budget directly affects the propensity of the credit officer to discriminate, which leads to the next proposition.

Proposition 3: If the MFI offers the optimal incentive premium, then the officer's propensity not to let prejudice interfere with loan granting is a decreasing function of the MFI's budget: $\frac{\partial \lambda^*}{\partial B} \geq 0$.

Proof: If $\tilde{s} \geq d$, the officer exerts no discrimination: $\lambda^* = 1$. If $\tilde{s} < d$, Eq. (17) shows that

$\frac{\partial \lambda^*}{\partial s^*} = \frac{1}{d} > 0$ and, from Proposition 2, we have: Then, Eq. (15) implies that:

$$\frac{\partial \lambda^*}{\partial B} = \frac{\partial \lambda^*}{\partial s^*} \frac{\partial s^*}{\partial B} = \frac{1}{d} \frac{\partial s^*}{\partial B} \geq 0.$$

MFIs receiving more generous subsidies can pay larger incentive premia to their loan officers. Biased officers will therefore reduce their propensity to discriminate more strongly than they would do otherwise. As a result, they will act more in line with the MFI's mission statement, and serve a higher fraction of poor clients from the D group.

Propositions 2 and 3 describe how pro-poor subsidized MFIs address the double bottom line of serving the poor and combatting discrimination. These propositions may be interpreted from the positive and normative standpoints. From the positive standpoint, the propositions imply that pro-poor MFIs that attract more subsidies are able to provide more powerful incentives not to discriminate. From the normative standpoint, Propositions 2 and 3 mean that pro-poor MFIs enforcing the ethical principle of no-discriminatory treatment of its

applicants should adjust the amount of resources it allocates to combatting discrimination to the amount of subsidies it receives.²⁴

Proposition 3 implies that a cut in subsidies may lead the MFI to decrease its anti-discrimination premium. Doing otherwise would require reducing too heavily the number of loans granted. As a result, reducing subsidies to discrimination-conscious pro-poor MFIs may result in an increase in discrimination exerted by loan officers. This result is important, because subsidies are known to enhance social performances (D'Espallier *et al.*, 2013). However, the typical social performances considered by scholars include the average loan size, the number of clients, and the interest rate charged to micro-borrowers, but not the reduction of bias in loan granting. Arguably, the subsidization of MFIs is chiefly motivated by financial inclusion of disadvantaged people. Since a no-discriminatory environment is key in levelling the playing field, we contend that anti-discrimination devices should be considered by donors as part of MFIs' social performances.

4. Concluding Remarks

Governance issues are more complex in socially-oriented organizations than in profit-oriented firms (Labie, 2001; Hartarska, 2005; Mersland, 2009). Stakeholders are less likely to tolerate malpractice in general and discrimination in particular, from socially-oriented institutions than are shareholders and customers of profit-oriented firms. Discrimination is also harder to tackle in welfare-maximizing institutions, where the profit-seeking mindset is lacking, a point raised by Aubert *et al.* (2009). As a consequence, we define discriminatory micro-lending as denying loans more frequently and/or granting loans with more stringent terms on the basis of observable characteristics unrelated to both creditworthiness and the MFI's mission. This approach accounts for the specific characteristics of double bottom-line institutions such as NGOs involved in microcredit lending. Providing an extended definition of discrimination can therefore be viewed as the first contribution of this paper.

²⁴ The normative dimension is central. As discrimination is difficult to observe, Propositions 2 and 3 are hardly falsifiable.

In line with this definition, we discuss how a socially-oriented MFI may mitigate discrimination by offering high-powered incentives. Using a formal agency model, we argue that well-designed incentive schemes might reduce discriminatory loan allocation to micro-entrepreneurs. However, because incentives are costly and budgets limited, MFIs may sometimes fulfill their mission more effectively by not fully eradicating discrimination. In a nutshell, when all borrowers exhibit the same creditworthiness, a non-discriminatory MFI may tolerate some discrimination because eradicating it would be too costly in terms of outreach.

One could, however, object that some discriminated-against groups of micro-entrepreneurs exhibit higher probabilities of default either because they are *ex ante* poorer than others or because discrimination attitudes prevalent in the global population will *ex post* compromise the success of their business. However, according to our strict definition, MFIs would not discriminate against these groups under such circumstances by granting them less favorable credit conditions. Sad thought it be, acknowledging that some segments of the population exhibit higher credit risk for any real reason can be viewed as unfair in a loose sense, but this definitely does not fall under our definition of discriminatory practice. This is because objectively assessing credit risk is part of the loan officer's job. Nevertheless, to address those kinds of social injustice, MFIs could adopt loan-granting policies based on affirmative action, but these policies will unsurprisingly prove costly (Hudon and Sandberg, 2013).

The costs associated with discrimination are difficult to assess. They are opportunity costs for both the MFI and the under-served population. However, most microfinance markets are supply-driven. Therefore, discrimination does not necessarily impede growth and profitability, and many MFIs may see it as cost-free. Nevertheless, competition is increasing (McIntosh and Wydick, 2005), and discrimination may ultimately become costly to MFIs. Leaving ethical considerations aside, anti-discrimination measures in access to credit could be needed from an economic development perspective.

More generally, designing adequate incentives in microfinance is delicate, as illustrated by the development of the sector. Initially, incentive schemes used by MFIs were based on a single criterion, typically the growth of loan portfolio. Over time, it appeared that growth targets were often met at the expense of credit quality. Consequently, today's MFIs

increasingly use a combination of criteria. Even so, the adjustment of loan officers to whatever set of incentives generates biases.²⁵ Incentives are thus no quick fix against discrimination in microfinance. Additionally, anti-discrimination measures might paradoxically make the MFI deviate from its mission. It has been argued, for instance by Coate and Loury (1993), that such measures may in fact hurt the very population they aim to help, by reinforcing stereotypes. What can MFIs do to combat discriminatory loan allocation by its loan officers then? First, they could adopt a hiring policy directed at loan officers biased in favor of discriminated-against groups. Interestingly, Biggs *et al.* (2002) put forward how staff members' ethnic networks influence who gets access to credit. Identifying loan officers with a bias in favor of disabled customers may, however, prove difficult, but the hiring of disabled loan officers could be tried. Second, MFIs could organize sensitivity training for their loan officers. For example, Bwire *et al.* (2009) report that MFIs doubled their number of disabled customers after their staff had participated in a two-hour disability awareness seminar. Moreover, we find that the probability to discriminate decreases when a person has a disabled relative. This suggests that tastes in discrimination are not static.

Microfinance practices have so far been studied in terms of efficiency and market segments. These factors largely explain why some poor people are served by MFIs while others remain unserved. But other reasons, such as discrimination, might be at work. We argue here that discrimination by MFIs deserves more attention than it has received so far. This contribution is intended to pave the way for conducting further in-field investigations of discriminatory practices and designing suitable anti-discrimination tools aligned with MFIs' social mission.

²⁵ As an example, Pamecas, a major network of credit unions in Senegal, set up a scheme mixing two indicators: portfolio quality (measured by arrears) and growth (measured by outstanding debt). By not including the number of loans, Pamecas created an incentive for loan officers to focus on borrowers requiring sound but larger loans, therefore favoring mission drift and ultimately leading Pamecas to reconsider its policy.

5. References

- Agier I. and A. Szafarz (2011), “Credit to women entrepreneurs: The curse of the trustworthier sex,” Université Libre de Bruxelles, WP-CEB: No 11-005.
- Agier, I. and A. Szafarz (2013a), “Subjectivity in credit allocation to micro-entrepreneurs: Evidence from Brazil,” *Small Business Economics*, 41(1): 263-75.
- Agier, I. and A. Szafarz (2013b), “Microfinance and gender: Is there a glass ceiling on loan size?” *World Development*, 42: 165–81.
- Allet, M. and M. Hudon (2013), “Green microfinance: Characteristics of microfinance institutions involved in environmental management,” *Journal of Business Ethics*, 126(3): 395–414.
- Armendariz, B. and A. Szafarz (2011), “On mission drift in microfinance institutions,” in B. Armendariz and M. Labie (Eds), *The Handbook of Microfinance*, London-Singapore: World Scientific Publishing, 341–66.
- Arrow, K.J. (1973), “The theory of discrimination,” in O. Ashenfelter and A. Rees (Eds.), *Discrimination in Labor Markets*, Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 3–33.
- Aubert, C., A. de Janvry, and E. Sadoulet (2009), “Designing credit agent incentives to prevent mission drift in pro-poor microfinance institutions,” *Journal of Development Economics* 90(1): 153–62.
- Barnes, C. (1994), “Institutional discrimination, disabled people and interprofessional care,” *Journal of Interprofessional Care* 8(2): 203–12.
- Barnes, C. and M. Oliver (1995), “Disability rights: Rhetoric and reality in the UK,” *Disability and Society* 10(1): 111–116.
- Becker, G.S. (1957), *The Economics of Discrimination*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Beegle, K. and W.A. Stock (2003), “The labour market effects of disability discrimination law,” *Journal of Human Resources* 38(4): 806–59.
- Beisland, L.A. and R. Mersland (2012a), “Barriers to microfinance for disabled persons: Evidence from economically active persons in Uganda,” *Enterprise Development & Microfinance* 23(1): 11-24.
- Beisland, L.A. and R. Mersland (2012b), “The use of microfinance services among economically active disabled people – Evidence from Uganda,” *Journal of International Development* 24(S): 69-83.

- Benabou, R. and J. Tirole (2003), "Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation," *Review of Economic Studies* 70(3): 489-520.
- Besley, T.J. and M. Ghatak (2005), "Competition and incentives with motivated agents," *American Economic Review* 95(3): 616–36.
- Biggs T., M. Raturi, and P. Srivastava (2002), "Ethnic networks and access to credit: evidence from the manufacturing sector in Kenya," *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization* 49(4): 473–86.
- Black, H., R.L. Schweitzer, and L. Mandell (1978), "Discrimination in mortgage lending," *American Economic Review* 68(2): 186–91
- Blanc, A. (2010), "Disability and liminality: An analytical model," *ALTER: European Journal of Disability Research* 4(1): 38-47.
- Blanchard, L., B. Zhao, and J. Yinger (2008), "Do lenders discriminate against minority and women entrepreneurs?" *Journal of Urban Economics* 63(2): 467–97.
- Blanchflower, D.G., P.B. Levine, and D.J. Zimmerman (2003), "Discrimination in the small-business credit market," *Review of Economics and Statistics* 85(4): 930–43.
- Bostic, R.W. (2003), "A test of cultural affinity in home mortgage lending," *Journal of Financial Services Research* 23(2): 89-112.
- Brana, S. (2012), "Microcredit: An Answer to the gender problem in funding?" *Small Business Economics* 40: 87-100.
- Buvinic, M and M. Berger (1990), "Sex differences in access to a small enterprise development fund in Peru," *World Development* 18(5): 695–705.
- Bwire, F.N., R. Mersland, and G. Mukasa (2009), "Access to mainstream microfinance services for persons with disabilities - Lessons learned from Uganda," *Disability Studies Quarterly* 29(1).
- Cavalluzzo, K.S. and J. Wolken (2005), "Small Business Loan Turndowns, Personal Wealth, and Discrimination," *Journal of Business* 78(6): 2153–77.
- Cavalluzzo, K.S. and L.C. Cavalluzzo (1998), "Market structure and discrimination: The case of small businesses," *Journal of Money, Credit, and Banking* 30(4): 771–92.
- Coate, S. and G.C. Loury (1993), "Will affirmative-action policies eliminate negative stereotypes?" *American Economic Review* 83(5): 1220–40.
- Cornée, S. and A. Szafarz (2014), "Vive la différence: Social banks and reciprocity in the credit market," *Journal of Business Ethics* 125(3): 361–80.

- Cramm, J.M. and H. Finkenflügel (2008), “Exclusion of disabled people from microcredit in Africa and Asia: A literature study, Asia Pacific Disability,” *Rehabilitation Journal* 19(2): 15–33.
- Cull, R., A. Demirgüç-Kunt, and J. Morduch (2009), “Microfinance meets the market,” *Journal of Economic Perspectives* 23(1): 167–192.
- Cull, R., A. Demirgüç-Kunt, and J. Morduch (2011), “Microfinance tradeoffs: regulation, competition, and financing,” in *The Handbook of Microfinance*, London-Singapore: World Scientific Publishing, 141–57.
- D'Espallier, B., M. Hudon, and A. Szafarz (2013), “Unsubsidized microfinance institutions,” *Economics Letters* 120(2): 174–6.
- Développement International Desjardins (2003), “Accroître la performance d’employés d’institutions de microfinance: La rémunération incitative”, Outil 4, Direction principale de la systématisation et de l’instrumentalisation.
- Dowla, A. and D. Barua, (2006), *The Poor Always Pay Back. The Grameen II Story*, Bloomfield, USA: Kumarian Press, Inc.
- Dyer, S. (2003), *The Inclusion of Disabled People in Mainstream Microfinance Programmes*, London: Leonard Cheshire International.
- Dymski, G.A. (2006), “Discrimination in the credit and housing markets: Findings and challenges,” in W.M. Rodgers (Ed.) *Handbook on the Economics of Discrimination*, 215–59. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar.
- Ferguson, M.F. and S.R. Peters (1997), “Cultural affinity and lending discrimination: The impact of underwriting errors and credit risk distribution on applicant denial rates,” *Journal of Financial Services Research* 11(1-2): 153-67.
- Fletschner, D. (2009), “Rural women’s access to credit: Market imperfections and intra-household dynamics,” *World Development* 37(3): 618–31.
- Fuentes, G.A. (1996), “The use of village agents in rural credit delivery,” *Journal of Development Studies* 33(1): 188–209.
- Ghatak, M. and T.W. Guinnane (1999), “The economics of lending with joint liability: Theory and practice,” *Journal of Development Economics* 60(1): 195–228.
- Ghosh, S. and E. Van Tassel (2008), “A model of microfinance and mission drift,” Department of Economics, Florida Atlantic University, December.

- Hartarska, V. (2005), "Governance and performance of microfinance institutions in Central and Eastern Europe and the newly independent states," *World Development* 33(10): 1627–43.
- Hermes, N. and R. Lensink (2007), "The empirics of microfinance: What do we know?" *Economic Journal* 117(517): F1–10.
- Holtmann, M. and M. Grammling (2005), "A toolkit for designing and implementing staff incentives schemes," Microfinance Network & CGAP, Nairobi.
- Hudon, M. (2009), "Should access to credit be a right?" *Journal of Business Ethics*, 84(1): 17-28
- Hudon, M., and A. Périlleux (2014), "Surplus distribution and characteristics of social enterprises: Evidence from microfinance," *Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance* 54(2): 147-57.
- Hudon, M. and J. Sandberg (2013), "The ethical crisis in microfinance: Issues, findings, and implications," *Business Ethics Quarterly* 23(4): 561-589.
- Johansson-Stenman, O. (2008), "Who are the trustworthy, we think?" *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization* 68(3-4): 456–65.
- Johnson, W.G. and J. Lambrinos (1985), "Wage discrimination against handicapped men and women-" *Journal of Human Resources* 20(2): 264–77.
- Knight, J.B. (1985), "Caste discrimination in the Indian urban labour market," *Journal of Development Economics* 17(3): 277–307.
- Labie, M. (2001), "Corporate governance in microfinance organizations: A long and winding road," *Management Decision* 39(4): 296–301.
- Lewis, C. (2004), "Microfinance from the point of view of women with disabilities: Lessons from Zambia and Zimbabwe," *Gender & Development* 12(1): 28–39.
- Madajewicz, M. (2011), "Joint liability versus individual liability in credit contracts," *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization* 77(2): 107-23.
- Martinelli, E. and R. Mersland (2010), "Microfinance for people with disabilities," in Barron T. (Ed.), *Poverty and Disability*, London: Leonard Cheshire International.
- McIntosh, C. and B. Wydick (2005), "Competition and microfinance," *Journal of Development Economics* 78(2): 271–98.
- McKim, A. and M. Hughart (2005), "Staff incentives schemes in practice: Findings from a global survey of microfinance institutions," Microfinance Network & CGAP, Washington, D.C.

- Méon, P.-G. and A. Szafarz (2011), “The modern corporation as a safe haven for taste-based discrimination: An agency model of hiring decisions,” *Labour Economics* 18(4): 487–97.
- Mersland, R. (2009), “The Cost of ownership in microfinance organizations,” *World Development* 37(2): 469–78.
- Mersland, R. and Ø. Strøm (2010), “Microfinance mission drift?” *World Development* 38, 28–36.
- Mersland, R. and R. Ø. Strøm, (2012), “The past and future of microfinance innovations”, in Cumming D. (Ed), *The Oxford Handbook of Entrepreneurial Finance*. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Morduch, J. (1999), “The microfinance promise,” *Journal of Economic Literature* 37(4): 1569–614.
- Morgan, R.L. and M. Alexander (2005), “The employer’s perception: Employment of individuals with developmental disabilities”, *Journal of Vocational Rehabilitation*, 23(1): 39–49.
- Munnell, A.G., M.B. Tootell, L.E. Browne, and J. McEneaney (1992), “Mortgage Lending in Boston: Interpreting HMDA Data,” Federal Reserve Bank of Boston, working paper 92–7.
- Munnell, A.G., M.B. Tootell, L.E. Browne, and J. McEneaney (1996), “Mortgage lending in Boston: Interpreting HMDA data,” *American Economic Review* 86(1): 25–53.
- Nederhoff, A.J. (1985), “Methods for coping with social desirability bias: A review,” *European Journal of Social Psychology* 15: 263–80.
- Neufeldt, A.H. (1995), “Empirical dimensions of discrimination against disabled people,” *Health and Human Rights* 1(2): 174–89.
- Patrinos, H.A. (2000), “The cost of discrimination in Latin America,” *Studies in Comparative International Development* 35(2): 3-17.
- Peck, B. and L.T. Kirkbride (2001), “Why businesses don’t employ people with disabilities,” *Journal of Vocational Rehabilitation* 16(2): 71-75.
- Phelps, E.S. (1972), “The statistical theory of racism and sexism,” *American Economic Review* 65(4): 659–61.
- Schreiner, M. (2000), “Credit-scoring for microfinance: Can it work?” *Journal of Microfinance* 2(2): 105–18.

- Schreiner, M., M. Cortes-Fontcuberta, D.H. Graham, G. Coetzee, and N. Vink (1996), “Racial discrimination in hire/purchase lending in apartheid South Africa,” *Development Southern Africa* 13(6): 847–60.
- Storey, D.J. (2004), “Racial and gender discrimination in the micro firms credit market: Evidence from Trinidad and Tobago”, *Small Business Economics* 23(5): 401–22.
- Sukhadeo, T. (2002), “Oppression and denial: Dalit discrimination in the 1990s,” *Economic and Political Weekly* 37(6): 572–8.
- Tchakoute-Tchuigoua, H. (2010), “Is there a difference in performance by the legal status of microfinance institutions?” *Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance* 50(4): 436-42.
- Tchakoute-Tchuigoua, H. (2012), “Active risk management and loan contract terms: Evidence from rated microfinance institutions,” *Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance* 52(4), 427-37.
- Tulchin, D. (2003) “Microfinance's double bottom line,” Social Enterprise Associates for the MicroCapital Institute, USA.
- United Nations (2008), Convention on the rights of persons with disabilities, United Nations, New York.
- Warning, M. and E. Sadoulet (1998), “The performance of village intermediaries in rural credit delivery under changing penalty regimes: Evidence from Senegal,” *Journal of Development Studies* 35(1): 115–38.
- Wydick, B. (1999), “Can social cohesion be harnessed to repair market failures? Evidence from group lending in Guatemala,” *Economic Journal* 109: 463–475.
- Wydick, B. (2001), “Group lending under dynamic incentives as a borrower discipline device,” *Review of Development Economics* 5(3): 406–420.

Appendix: Additional Tables

*** Insert Table A1 here ***

*** Insert Table A2 here ***

*** Insert Table A3 here ***

*** Insert Table A4 here ***

List of Tables

Table 1: Ordered logit regression explaining the reaction to statement 1: “I believe that one of the reasons why we have few disabled customers is because we often unconsciously marginalize or discriminate them”

	(1.1)	(1.2)	(1.3)	(1.4)	(1.5)	(1.6)
Loan officer	0.696 (2.30)**		0.691 (2.27)**	0.666 (2.03)**	0.646 (1.89)*	0.713 (1.87)*
Higher default		0.0441 (0.34)	0.0665 (0.54)	0.113 (1.00)	0.0864 (0.76)	0.0756 (0.61)
Disabled relative				-0.587 (2.05)**	-0.583 (2.15)**	-0.597 (2.33)**
Woman					-0.314 (1.14)	-0.278 (0.93)
Work experience						0.0836 (0.82)
Observations	189	213	188	184	180	166
Log-pseudo-likelihood	-283.76	-327.43	-281.85	-273.43	-265.08	-242.43
Wald Chi ²	5.30	0.12	5.37	10.75	11.66	16.61
Pseudo R ²	0.0109	0.000481	0.0115	0.0181	0.0206	0.0229

Cluster-robust absolute z-statistics in parentheses, *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

Table 2: Ordered logit regressions explaining the reaction to statement 2: “I believe that in this branch we never discriminate people because of their disability”

	(2.1)	(2.2)	(2.3)	(2.4)	(2.5)	(2.6)
Loan officer	-0.612 (2.37)**		-0.62 (2.51)**	-0.615 (2.24)**	-0.655 (2.38)**	-0.744 (2.77)***
Higher default		-0.125 (0.87)	-0.13 (0.94)	-0.136 (0.91)	-0.142 (0.99)	-0.125 (0.77)
Disabled relative				0.0895 (0.25)	0.183 (0.5)	-0.000409 (0.00097)
Woman					-0.303 (0.97)	-0.316 (0.82)
Work experience						-0.14 (0.1)
Observations	187	210	186	182	179	165
Log pseudolikelihood	-260.60	-293.98	-257.47	-251.90	-245.34	-218.60
Wald Chi ²	5.63	0.76	7.41	8.04	21.14	25.15
Pseudo R ²	0.00833	0.00395	0.0128	0.013	0.016	0.0199

Cluster-robust absolute z-statistics in parentheses, *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

Table 3: Outcome of loan granting

Applicant 1 \ Applicant 2	(D,P)	(D,L)	(F,P)	(F,L)
(D,P)	(D,P)	(D,P)	(F,P)	(D,P) with prob. λ (F,P) with prob. $(1-\lambda)$
(D,L)	(D,P)	(D,L)	(F,P)	(F,L)
(F,P)	(F,P)	(F,P)	(F,P)	(F,P)
(F,L)	(D,P) with prob. λ (F,L) with prob. $(1-\lambda)$	(F,L)	(F,P)	(F,L)

Table 4: Welfare gain resulting from loan granting

Applicant 1 \ Applicant 2	(D,P)	(D,L)	(F,P)	(F,L)
(D,P)	Δu_p	Δu_p	Δu_p	Δu_p with prob. λ Δu_L with prob. $(1-\lambda)$
(D,L)	Δu_p	Δu_L	Δu_p	Δu_L
(F,P)	Δu_p	Δu_p	Δu_p	Δu_p
(F,L)	Δu_p with prob. λ Δu_L with prob. $(1-\lambda)$	Δu_L	Δu_p	Δu_L

A1: Distribution of ratings (in %)

Rating	<i>“I believe that one of the reasons why we have few disabled customers is because we often unconsciously marginalize or discriminate them”</i>	<i>“I believe that in this branch we never discriminate against people because of their disability”</i>	<i>“I believe that being disabled is associated with higher risk of loan default”</i>
1	22.81	22.67	30.84
2	15.35	6.67	24.67
3	9.21	8.44	14.98
4	29.82	15.11	11.89
5	17.11	45.78	11.89
n.a.	5.70	1.33	5.73
Total	100	100	100

1 = fully disagree, 2 = partly disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = partly agree, 5 = fully agree.

Table A2: Characteristics of MFIs

	Mean	Standard deviation
Share of loan officers	0.487	0.357
Share of employees with disabled relatives	0.384	0.192
Share of women	0.456	0.171
Share of employees with more than two years of experience	0.458	0.304

Table A3: Ordered logit regressions with the explained variable being the reaction to the statement 1: “I believe that one of the reasons why we have few disabled customers is because we often unconsciously marginalize or discriminate them”

	(A5.1)	(A5.2)	(A5.3)	(A5.4)	(A5.5)
Loan officer	0.805 (2.757)***	0.803 (2.737)***	0.776 (2.598)***	0.646 (2.225)**	0.893 (2.713)***
Higher default		0.0405 (0.490)	0.0808 (0.933)	0.0864 (0.993)	0.0364 (0.400)
Disabled relative			-0.465 (-1.410)	-0.583 (-1.738)*	-0.464 (-1.295)
Woman				-0.314 (-1.151)	-0.310 (-1.075)
Work experience					0.0802 (0.542)
Transformed MFI	0.874 (3.047)***	0.908 (3.138)***	0.903 (3.055)***		0.942 (2.982)***
Bank MFI	0.193 (0.389)	0.220 (0.441)	0.246 (0.493)		0.0252 (0.0413)
Sacco MFI	-0.198 (-0.143)	-0.0961 (-0.0690)	-0.158 (-0.113)		-39.08 (-1.43e-07)
Observations	189	188	184	180	166
Log pseudolikelihood	-278.69	-276.54	-268.39	-265.08	-236.35
Wald Chi ²	16.38	17.22	20.14	11.17	23.53
Pseudo R ²	0.0285	0.0302	0.0362	0.0206	0.0474

z-statistics in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Table A4: Ordered logit regressions with the explained variable being the reaction to the statement 2: “I believe that in this branch we never discriminate people because of their disability”

	(A6.1)	(A6.2)	(A6.3)	(A6.4)	(A6.5)
Loan officer	-0.541 (-1.785)*	-0.563 (-1.850)*	-0.557 (-1.803)*	-0.655 (-2.142)**	-0.705 (-2.119)**
Higher default		-0.124 (-1.440)	-0.131 (-1.433)	-0.142 (-1.563)	-0.123 (-1.271)
Disabled relative			0.0989 (0.292)	0.183 (0.532)	0.0214 (0.0589)
Woman				-0.303 (-1.073)	-0.295 (-0.990)
Work experience					-0.146 (-0.957)
Transformed MFI	0.00985 (0.0339)	0.0369 (0.126)	0.0201 (0.0666)		0.115 (0.365)
Bank MFI	-0.420 (-0.825)	-0.394 (-0.770)	-0.426 (-0.828)		0.0424 (0.0689)
Sacco MFI	0.732 (0.626)	0.509 (0.430)	0.497 (0.420)		31.66 (3.21e-06)
Observations	187	186	182	179	165
Log pseudolikelihood	-260	-257	-251.4	-245.34	-218.12
Wald Chi ²	5.600	7.617	7.659	7.966	9.865
Pseudo R ²	0.0107	0.0146	0.0150	0.0160	0.0221

z-statistics in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

List of Figures

Figure 1: Rating distributions for the statements on discrimination

Figure 1a: Statement 1: “we often discriminate

1 = fully disagree, 2 = partly disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = partly agree, 5 = fully agree.

Figure 1b: Statement 2: “we never discriminate”

1 = fully disagree, 2 = partly disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = partly agree, 5 = fully agree.